

Estimation of the Impact of Vaccination Intervention on Recovered Coronavirus Patients

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Abstract:

This work estimated the impact of vaccination intervention on coronavirus patients who have recovered from the disease and the vulnerability index of the recovered population due to the impact of vaccine was also investigated. This work adopted a numerical solution to study the continuous dynamical system of linear first order differential equations describing a SEIR (Susceptible, Exposed, Infected, Recovered) model on the spread of Coronavirus Disease – 2019 (COVID-19). To tackle this problem, MATLAB ordinary differential equation of order 45 (ODE45) numerical method was adopted for the analysis. The vulnerability index of the

recovered population was low due to the impact of vaccine meaning that the recovered population will gain immunity and they will not be re-infected. The study recommended that coronavirus patients who have recovered from the disease should ensure that they have vaccination administered to them to avoid re-occurrence of the virus attack as an intervention strategy.

Keywords: *Vaccination, Intervention, Coronavirus, Recovered, Modelling.*

Introduction

The novel coronavirus disease – 2019 (COVID-19) is an infectious disease that is deadly which was first reported in Wuhan City, Hubei Province in China by the end of the year 2019 (Mackolil & Mahanthesh, 2020). Cases were all linked to Wuhan's Human Seafood Wholesale Market, which trades in fish and mathematical livestock (Sohrabi, et al., 2020; Ezimadu, et al, 2020). From China, the disease spread to other parts of the world causing deaths. The rapid

spread of the disease was due to the fact that COVID-19 emergence coincided with the largest annual human migration in the world that is the spring festival travel season (Lin, et al., 2020). The spread was so enormous that it grew from an epidemic status to a pandemic status, as declared by WHO, in January, 2020 (Okwonu, et al, 2020, 2021). Clinical symptoms of COVID-19 are dry cough, vomiting, fever, and diarrhea and the virus can be transmitted from an infected individual to a healthy individual.

According to Annas, et al (2020), coronavirus can be easily spread through small droplets from the nose or mouth of an infected person via sneezing or coughing. It belongs to the family of coronavirus, of order Nidovirales (Chen, et al., 2020). Coronavirus are large, positive sense RNA (Ribonucleic acid) virus comprising of four genera: alpha, beta, delta and gamma (Ali, et al., 2020). The virus inflicted a lot of burden on the health sector and also affected the economy. There are a lot of intervention strategies to control the spread of the disease which include social distancing, use of face masks in public places, vaccination, tracing of contacts, washing of hands frequently with soap under running water, community lockdown, use of sanitizers, quarantining of suspected cases, isolating of confirmed cases. Nigeria reported her first case of COVID-19 on February 27, 2020 when an Italian citizen who worked in Nigeria was diagnosed of the disease upon returning back to Nigeria from a trip to Milan, Italy (Iboi, et al., 2020). In March 2020, the government imposed a lockdown to curb the spread of the disease and the lockdown lasted for months.

There are a lot of models that serve as a means to study the behavior of diseases. These models show the relationship between the disease and human compartments using mathematical equations. In these models, the entire population is divided into compartments or classes where each group represents a specific stage of the pandemic (Dadlani, et al., 2013; Okposo, et al, 2023). An example of such mathematical model is SIR (Susceptible, Infected, Recovered) model which is also known as compartmental disease model postulated by Kermack and Mckendrick (1927), Aderibigbe and Apanapudor (2014 and Iwebodo, et al. (2023). They divided the population into three classes namely susceptible (S), infected (I) and recovered (R). They assumed that all individuals are susceptible to the disease and people only gain complete immunity after recovery from infection. Susceptible-Infectious-Susceptible (SIS) model assumes that once an individual recovers from a disease, the individual becomes susceptible again to the same disease he/she recovered from and this means that the

individuals do not gain natural immunity (Jit & Marc, 2011).

According to Dadlani, et al (2013), the SIRS [susceptible (S), infected (I), recovered (R) and susceptible (S)] model is an extension of the SIR (Susceptible, Infected, Recovered) model where it is believed that individuals can become susceptible again even after recovering from the disease. SEIR (Susceptible-Exposed-Infected-Recovered) model divides the population into four classes namely Susceptible (S), Exposed (E), Infected (I) and Recovered (R). SEIR model considered the fact that some individuals may have symptoms of the disease but they have not been detected (exposed population). Presently in Nigeria, there is a COVID-19 vaccine which boosts immunity against the disease, accelerates COVID-19 healing and reduces transmission of the disease. Nigeria started COVID-19 vaccination on 5th March, 2021 to curb the pandemic. The vaccine is against severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), the virus that causes coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19).

A mathematical model to study the effect of an imperfect anti-COVID-19 vaccine on COVID-19 pandemic in the United States of America was used by Iboi, et al (2020). Their results showed that if at least eighty two percentage of the population in United States of America that are prone to the infection are vaccinated with an anti-COVID-19 vaccine that has an assumed efficacy of eight percentage, vaccine-induced community herd immunity will be achieved which will reduce the possibility of disease spread. They also stated that combination of vaccination program with other intervention strategies such as use of face mask and social distancing will increase the prospect of eradicating COVID-19 in the United States.

The transmission risk of the novel coronavirus (2019-n-CoV) infection and its implication for interventions of public health using a deterministic compartmental model was estimated by Tang, et al. (2020) and Okposo, et al. (2023). They concluded that public health interventions such as tracing of contacts, quarantine of susceptible population, isolation

of infected population can reduce the risk of transmission of the disease coupled with restrictions on travelling. Ivorra, et al (2020) studied the mathematical modelling of the spread of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) with consideration of the undetected infections using China as a case study was studied. Their key result revealed that imposition of preventive measures was effective in controlling the spread of the disease and early detection of COVID-19 cases reduced the magnitude of the epidemic. Moghadas, et al (2021), studied the impact of vaccination on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreaks in the United States using an agent-based model of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) transmission. They discovered in their results that vaccination reduced the overall attack rate, adverse outcomes with non-intensive care unit hospitalizations, intensive care unit hospitalizations and deaths. They concluded that vaccination can have a huge effect on lessening the outbreak of COVID-19. (Okwonu, et al, 2021; Apanapudor, et al., 2023), proposed robust multivariate correlation techniques to determine the strength of the association between two or more variables while examining confirmation analysis using Covid -19 data set.

An assessment of the real-world impact of vaccination on coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) incidence in healthcare personnel at an academic medical center was carried out by Waldman, et al (2021). Their results showed a decrease in the incidence rate of the virus among the healthcare personnel following administration of vaccine. They also stated that unvaccinated healthcare were at a higher risk of infection. A prediction of the impact of vaccination and active case finding measures in the control of the epidemic of coronavirus disease in a migrant-populated area in Thailand was done by Suphanchaimat, et al (2021). They concluded that a combination of vaccination and active case finding measures led to a reduction in the number of COVID-19 cases and deaths compared to the use of only a single measure. A similar approach was also demonstrated by (Okwonu, et al, 2022) while discussing robust

hybrid classification methods and applications. They considered pairs of observations (X,Y) in n-dimension where Y is the dependent variable and X the independent variable to predict the linear relationship between these variables.

Materials and Methods

Model Formulation

The interaction between the populations of the susceptible humans, the exposed humans, the infected humans and the recovered humans which are time dependent is studied by formulating a system of linear ordinary differential equations. The formulation of this mathematical model describes an aspect of coronavirus which define a set of deterministic parameter values with application in the control of coronavirus. The SEIR mathematical model on the spread of COVID-19, divided into four compartments namely: Susceptible (S), Exposed (E), Infected (I) and Recovered (R) is a modified Annas et al. (2020) model. Susceptible population (S) are the individuals that have no immunity to the disease, hence, they can be infected. Exposed population (E) are individuals who are already infected but they are yet to be detected. Infected population (I) represent individuals who have already been infected by the virus and can transmit it to healthy individuals. Recovered population (R) are individuals who have been cured of the disease.

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = \pi - \alpha IS - \mu S + VR,$$

$$S(0) = S_0 \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \alpha IS - (\beta + \mu)E,$$

$$E(0) = E_0 \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = \beta E - (\delta + d + \mu)I,$$

$$I(0) = I_0 \geq 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = \delta I - VR - \mu R,$$

$$R(0) = R_0 \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

subject to the initial conditions $S(t) \geq 0, E(t) \geq 0, I(t) \geq 0$ and $R(t) \geq 0$. Here, $S(t), E(t), I(t)$ and $R(t)$ represent susceptible, exposed, infected and recovered populations at time t .

Figure 1. Flowchart of the SEIR Model

Table 1. Variables and Parameters of the Model

Parameter	Definition	Estimated mean value
$S(t)$	Population of Susceptible population at time t	330,928
$E(t)$	Population of Exposed population at time t	254,560
$I(t)$	Population of Infected population at time t	2,354
$R(t)$	Population of Recovered population at time t	249,064
μ	Natural death rate	6.25×10^{-3}
α	Probability of changing from Suspected to Exposed	0.2308
β	Probability of changing from Exposed to Infected	0.9908
d	Rate of death due to COVID-19 infection	4.3041
δ	Probability of changing from Infected to Recovered	0.9905
V	Vaccination rate of recovered individuals	0.02
Π	Recruitment rate of susceptible individuals	0.45

It was assumed that the total population was of constant size at time t , and individuals in the infected population can infect healthy people. Furthermore, it was assumed that the exposed population, even though they were undetected, also had the capacity to infect people. The susceptible population can be infected by both the exposed and infected population. Also, individuals move from one class to the other as their status with respect to the disease evolves.

Steady State Solution

A dynamical system is said to reach a steady state or state of equilibrium if the variables which define the behavior of the system are unchanging at time t . This implies that if a system is in a steady state at time t_0 , it will stay there for all times $t \geq t_0$. From analysis of linear stability, a steady-state solution is said to be stable if the real parts of all the eigenvalues of

the Jacobian at the steady state solution are negative.

At an equilibrium point, all rates of change are equal to zero. That is, $\frac{dS}{dt} = \frac{dE}{dt} = \frac{dI}{dt} = \frac{dR}{dt} = 0$. Hence equation (1) – (4) become

$$\pi - \alpha IS - \mu S + VR = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha IS - (\beta + \mu)E = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\beta E - (\delta + d + \mu)I = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\delta I - VR - \mu R = 0 \quad (8)$$

Disease Free Equilibrium for COVID-19

At disease free-state, there is no spread of COVID-19. This implies that there is neither exposed nor infected nor recovered population, that is, $E = I = R = 0$.

From equation (5),

$$\pi - \alpha IS - \mu S + VR = 0, \quad \text{since } I = R = 0$$

$$S = \frac{\pi}{\mu} \quad (9)$$

Therefore, the equilibrium points of disease-free for COVID-19 are:

$$(S_0, E_0, I_0, R_0) = \left(\frac{\pi}{\mu}, 0, 0, 0\right) \quad (10)$$

Endemic Equilibrium for COVID-19

At endemic equilibrium points, there is the possibility of the spread of COVID-19 and in endemic conditions, $S \neq 0$, $E \neq 0$, $I \neq 0$ and $R \neq 0$. Using equation (5) – (8) to solve for the state variables gives

$$S = \frac{c_1 c_2}{\beta \alpha} = S^* \quad (11)$$

$$E = \frac{c_2 (c_1 c_2 c_3 \mu - c_3 \beta \alpha \pi)}{\beta \alpha (\beta V \delta - c_1 c_2 c_3)} = E^* \quad (12)$$

$$I = \frac{c_3 (c_1 c_2 \mu - \beta \alpha \pi)}{\alpha (\beta V \delta - c_1 c_2 c_3)} = I^* \quad (13)$$

$$R = \frac{\delta (c_1 c_2 \mu - \beta \alpha \pi)}{\alpha (\beta V \delta - c_1 c_2 c_3)} = R^* \quad (14)$$

where,

$$c_1 = \beta + \mu, c_2 = \delta + d + \mu, c_3 = \mu + V$$

Hence, the endemic equilibrium point is $(S, E, I, R) = (S^*, E^*, I^*, R^*)$

Results and Discussion

Since the dynamical system does not have a closed form solution, the functions which are interacting were coded in a MATLAB computer programming language so as to study the behavior of the system (Baker & Rihan, 1999; Baker et al., 2005). According to Gilat (2013), MATLAB stands for matrix laboratory and it can be used for mathematical computations, modeling and simulations, data analysis and processing. To obtain the plots in Figure 2-5, the parameter values in Table 1 were used to evaluate equations (1) – (4) with the variation of the vaccination rate of recovered individuals.

Figure 2. The Impact of Vaccination Rate on the Recovered Population at $V=0.002$ Using a MATLAB ODE45 Numerical Scheme

Figure 3. The Impact of Vaccine on the Recovered Population at $V=0.01$ Using a MATLAB ODE45 Numerical Scheme.

Figure 4. The impact of vaccine on the recovered population at $v=0.022$ using a MATLAB ODE45 numerical scheme.

Figure 5. The impact of vaccine on the recovered population at $V=0.03$ using a MATLAB ODE45 numerical scheme.

Vaccination boosts immunity against the disease and reduces transmission of the disease. For

recovered individuals, vaccination will prevent them from being re-infected with the disease and if they gain immunity, it means that the disease will gradually fade out of the population. At a low rate of vaccination, the recovered individuals will be susceptible to the disease which will lead to an increase in the transmission of the disease. When the rate of vaccination is increased, more individuals will gain immunity against the virus which will reduce the rate of spread of the disease.

Conclusion

This work has significantly adopted a numerical solution to study the continuous dynamical system of a linear first order differential equation describing a SEIR (Susceptible, Exposed, Infected, Recovered) model. The vulnerability index of the recovered population was low due to the impact of vaccine meaning that the recovered population will gain immunity and they will not be re-infected. This is an indication that the disease will go to extinction over a long period of time with the introduction of vaccine. This result will help the public health policy makers in adopting the best strategy in mitigation of coronavirus. These findings agree with that of Moghadas et al. (2021) whose result showed that vaccination can have a huge effect on lessening the outbreak of COVID-19. This study also agrees with Annas et al. (2020) whose result indicated that COVID-19 will hasten the healing of individuals affected by the disease. The study recommends that the recovered population should ensure that they have vaccination administered to them to avoid incidence of virus attack as an intervention strategy.

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